

SYNTHESIS OF OPTICALLY ACTIVE POLY(SILYLETHYLENE)S CONTAINING A STEREOGENIC SILICON CENTER

Xinhua Wan, Hoi Sing Kwok and Ben Zhong Tang

*Department of Chemistry and Center for Display Research
Hong Kong University of Science & Technology, Clear Water Bay, Kowloon, Hong Kong*

Abstract — Hydrosilylation of acetylene with a chiral silane, *R*-(+)-methyl-1-naphthyl-phenylsilane [*R*-(+)-Me-NpPhSi*H], in the presence of $H_2PtCl_6 \cdot xH_2O$ proceeds with retention of configuration of the stereogenic silicon center and produces a chiral vinylsilane or silylethylene [*S*-(+)-MeNpPhSi*Vi] of high optical purity under mild condition (50°C) in high chemical yield (85%). Anionic polymerizations of the chiral silylethylene monomer by an achiral initiator *n*-BuLi yield optically active polymers with $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ up to -28.1° , while polymerizations of the racemic monomer by a chiral initiator *n*-BuLi/(-)-sparteine produce polymers with $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ up to $+275^\circ$. Thus the sign of optical rotation of the polymers can be controlled by different combination of monomer and catalyst. Magnitude of the optical rotation can be "tuned" by changing polymerization temperature with high temperature generally favoring random propagation. All the polymers have low polydispersity indexes (M_w/M_n down to 1.02) or possess narrow molecular weight distributions. Spectroscopic characterization confirms the molecular structure of polymers to be poly(silylethylene), that is, a polyethylene main chain with a bulky methyl-1-naphthyl-phenylsilyl side chain. The polymers are thermally stable (onset temperature for weight loss in air: 380°C), possess high glass transition temperature ($T_g > 380^\circ C$), and may find a wide range of applications in the optical display systems.

INTRODUCTION

While great research efforts have been devoted to chiral carbon chemistry, chiral silicon chemistry has received much less attention, and optically active polymers containing stereogenic silicon centers are almost unknown [1-3]. Optically active polymers possess many unique properties which are often difficult or impossible to achieve with optically inactive polymers. For example, optically active polymers are promising candidates for "molecular electronics" materials such as ferroelectric liquid crystals, nonlinear optical assemblies, optical data storage media, etc. [4].

We are interested in synthesizing optically active polymers containing stereogenic silicon centers. In 1989, we prepared a chiral silicon-containing polyacetylene and discovered a novel electro-optical application for the optically active polymer in the liquid crystal display system [5-7]. In our previous work, we

incorporated the chiral methyl-1-naphthylphenylsilyl group into the acetylene monomer via an alkyl spacer. In this work, we synthesized a chiral silicon-containing vinyl monomer, *S*-(+)-MeNpPhSi*Vi, by direct reaction of a chiral silane with acetylene via Pt-catalyzed hydrosilylation. We here demonstrate that we can synthesize optically active poly(silylethylene)s by polymerizing either the chiral monomer using an achiral initiator (*n*-BuLi) or the corresponding racemic monomer using a chiral initiator [*n*-BuLi/(-)-sparteine].

EXPERIMENTAL

All polymerization reactions were conducted in Schlenk tubes under an atmosphere of oxygen-free dry dinitrogen. In a typical run, 0.63 ml of a 1.6 M hexane solution of *n*-BuLi was admixed with 4.37 ml of freshly distilled toluene in a baked 10-ml Schlenk tube. In another Schlenk tube a monomer solution was prepared by dissolving 0.55 g of *S*-(+)-MeNpPhSi*Vi in 0.44 ml toluene, to which 0.5 ml of the pre-prepared catalyst solution was added using a hypodermic syringe. After stirring at 40°C under dinitrogen for 24 h, the polymerization was terminated by adding 1 drop of methanol to the reaction mixture. After diluting with 3 ml of toluene, the reaction mixture was added into a large amount (30 ml) of methanol with stirring. The precipitated polymer was filtered through a fine glass filter and dried under vacuum to a constant weight. White powder; yield: 0.16 g (29%). M_n (by GPC on the basis of a polystyrene calibration): 3220; M_w/M_n : 1.04. $[\alpha]_D^{20} -28.1^\circ$ (*c* 1.25, THF). 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ (ppm) -0.8-2.5 (br, aliphatic protons in CH_3 , CH_2 , and CH), 5.8-8.3 (br, aromatic protons in Ph and Np).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stereochemistry in hydrosilylation

While addition of various silanes to alkynes has been extensively studied, there have been no reports on hydrosilylation of alkynes by optically active silanes [8-9]. In 1992, Gevorgyan et al. carried out hydrosilylation of alkynes by racemic MeNpPhSiH in the presence of Pt-catalysts [8], but stereochemistry of the

hydrosilylation remains unknown because of the racemic nature of the silane starting material they used. Hydrosilylation of alkynes by chiral silanes would lead to a variety of optically active silylalkene monomers, and it is of interest to know whether the reactions proceed with retention or inversion of the configuration of the stereogenic silicon center. We thus prepared a chiral silane *R*-(+)-MeNpPhSi*H according to Sommer and Holt's procedures [10-11]. Gevorgyan et al. used H₂PtCl₆(cyclohexanone) complex to catalyze the hydrosilylation of acetylene by the racemic MeNp-PhSiH. We directly used a commercially available H₂PtCl₆·xH₂O catalyst to hydrosilylate acetylene by the chiral silane (scheme 1). The reaction went smoothly under mild heating (50°C) and an optically active silylethylene was obtained in high yield (85%). Optical rotation of the silylethylene was found to be +1.21°. According to Corriu and Royo's correlation [12], the absolute configuration of the silylethylene is *S*; that is, the hydrosilylation proceeds with retention of the configuration of the stereogenic center. Corriu and Royo prepared *S*-(+)-MeNpPhSi*Vi by coupling (-)-NpPhViSi*Cl with MeMgI, and optical rotation value of their product was +0.75° [12]. They also carried out reactions of MeLi with (+)-NpPhViSi*H, (+)-NpPhViSi*OMe, and (+)-NpPhViSi*F, and optical rotation values of the resulting *R*-(-)-MeNpPhSi*Vi were -1.0, -0.6, and -0.55, respectively [12]. Although the starting material we used was not 100% optically pure, the hydrosilylation product had higher [α]_D²⁰ value than those prepared by Corriu and Royo using the above-mentioned reactions, implying that insertion of the Pt center into Si*-H bond proceeds with a high degree of retention of configuration at Si* and that product formation takes place in a highly stereospecific manner. In other words, the hydrosilylation is a better way for preparing the chiral silylethylene with higher optical purity.

Scheme 1

Polymerization of chiral monomer by achiral initiator

We first used the racemic silylethylene monomer MeNpPhSiVi to test polymerization conditions. We attempted to polymerize the monomer by such typical radical initiators as AIBN and BPO, but failed to obtain even trace amount of polymeric product either in bulk or in solution in a wide temperature range. The monomer was not susceptible to radical polymerization. *n*-BuLi is a commonly-used initiator for anionic polymerization. We tried to polymerize the silylethylene at low temperature (-78°C-0°C), but again failed to isolate any polymeric product. However, when we carried out the anionic polymerization at 20°C for 24 h,

methanol-insoluble white powdery polymer was isolated in 48% yield (Table 1 no. 2). GPC analysis of the polymer gave a sharp peak, from which M_n and M_w/M_n of the polymer were estimated (relative to polystyrene) to be 8933 and 1.14, respectively. When we increased the polymerization temperature to 55°C, the polymer yield increased to 87% and the polydispersity index decreased to 1.03. Further increase in the polymerization temperature further increased the polymer yield and narrowed the molecular weight distribution although M_n of the polymer undesirably decreased.

It has been become clear that the silylethylene monomer undergoes *n*-BuLi-initiated anionic polymerization at around ambient temperatures. We thus investigated anionic polymerization of the chiral monomer by the achiral initiator. The chiral monomer did undergo polymerization at 25°C, but much to our surprise, both the yield and M_n of the polymer were rather low. However, the polymer was optically active, whose [α]_D²⁰ was found to be -15.8° (Table 1 no. 5). Both the polymer yield and M_n increased when the polymerization temperature was increased to 40°C, and even better the polymer had narrower molecular weight distribution and higher optical rotation value. Further increase in temperature, however, had undesirable effects on the polymerization reaction: the polymer yield and M_n decreased, the polydispersity broadened, and the optical rotation also decreased. This is probably due to the instability of the active center at the high temperature, which favors random polymerization and lowers tacticity of the resulting polymer. It is noteworthy that the polymerization behavior of the chiral monomer was so different from that of its racemic counterpart. Further study on the reaction mechanisms should help us understand the stereochemistry involved in the polymerizations.

Table 1
Anionic Polymerization of (methyl-1-naphthylphenylsilyl)ethylene initiated by *n*-BuLi^a

No.	Temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	M_n^b	M_w/M_n^b	[α] _D ^{20c} (deg.)
Racemic monomer					
1	0	0			
2	20	48	8933	1.14	
3	55	87	5490	1.03	
4	60	93	4118	1.02	
Chiral monomer^d					
5	25	15	927	1.14	-15.8
6	40	29	3220	1.04	-28.1
7	55	27	1006	1.27	-9.5

^a In toluene for 24 h; [M]₀ = 2 M, [cat.] = 0.1 M.

^b Determined by GPC on the basis of a polystyrene calibration. ^c In THF. ^d [α]_D²⁰ +1.21°.

Polymerization of racemic monomer by chiral initiator

It is attractive to synthesize optically active polymers from racemic monomers by chiral initiators. *n*-BuLi/(+)-DDB is an effective chiral initiator for the stereoselective polymerization of some methacrylates [13], but did not work for the polymerization of our racemic silylethylene monomer. Neither of the attempted polymerizations carried out at 20°C and 40°C succeeded (Table 2 nos. 1-2). *n*-BuLi/(+)-camphene could polymerize the racemic monomer, but the resulting polymers were optically inactive. When *n*-BuLi/(-)-sparteine was used at 20°C, a small amount of polymer was isolated. Unfortunately, however, the polymer was insoluble in THF. This is probably because the chiral active center preferentially polymerizes one enantiomer, thus forming a polymer chain with a tightly-packed helical conformation. This hypothesis was supported by the high optical rotation power of the polymer: The polymer was partially soluble in dioxane, and the filtered dioxane solution exhibited an $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ value as high as +275° (Table 2 no. 5). When the polymerization temperature was increased to 40°C, the polymer yield increased but the optical rotation of the polymer decreased dramatically. This might be because the stereospecificity of the active center decreases with increasing temperature, allowing another enantiomer to participate in the propagation reaction, thus increasing the yield but decreasing the $[\alpha]_D^{20}$. At 60°C, more polymer was produced but the resulting polymer was optically completely inactive, although its molecular weight distribution remained to be very narrow.

Table 2

Anionic polymerization of (methyl-1-naphthylphenylsilyl)-ethylene initiated by chiral catalysts^a

No.	Temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	M_n^b	M_w/M_n^b	$[\alpha]_D^{20c}$ (deg.)
<i>n</i> -BuLi/(+)-DDB ^d					
1	20	0			
2	40	0			
<i>n</i> -BuLi/(+)-camphene					
3	20	20	1237	1.23	0
4	40	56	1481	1.26	0
<i>n</i> -BuLi/(-)-sparteine					
5	20	21	nd ^e	nd ^e	+275 ^f
6	40	50	4349	1.06	+1.7
7	60	83	4751	1.04	0

^a In toluene for 24 h; $[M]_0 = 2$ M, $[n\text{-BuLi}] = 0.1$ M, $[R^*] = 0.12$ M. ^b Determined by GPC on the basis of a polystyrene calibration. ^c In THF except no. 5. ^d (*S,S*)-(+)-2,3-Dimethoxy-1,4-bis(dimethylamino)butane. ^e Not determined (insoluble in THF). ^f For dioxane-soluble fraction.

Structure and properties

The molecular structure of the polymers was characterized spectroscopically. The silylethylene monomer absorbed at 1590, 1402, and 956 cm^{-1} due to C=C stretching, =CH₂ scissoring, and =C-H wagging vibrations, respectively. While the contribution from the aromatic absorption remained, the polymer showed no olefinic absorption bands in its IR spectrum (Fig. 1). The absorption peaks at 5.82, 6.21, and 6.64 ppm from the olefinic protons in the monomer completely disappeared in the ¹H NMR spectrum of the polymer (Fig. 2). New peaks from methine (CH) and methylene (CH₂) protons in the polymer backbone appeared in the range of 0.7-2.5 ppm. The absorption peak of the methyl (Si-CH₃) protons shifted upfield because of the loss of the deshielding effect of the vinyl group. We compared the spectroscopic data for the racemic and chiral polymers, but found no noticeable difference.

Fig. 1. IR spectra of (A) (methyl-1-naphthylphenylsilyl)ethylene monomer and (B) its polymer (KBr, rt; sample from Table 1 no. 2).

The poly(silylethylene)s were thermally stable. As can be seen from Fig. 3, the onset temperature for weight loss from the polymer in air was as high as 380°C. The high thermal stability of the polymer might be due to so-called "jacket effect" of the side chain [14]. The polymer main chain "wears" a "jacket" of side chains consisting of bulky methyl-1-naphthylphenylsilyl groups, which protects the polyethylene backbone from the attack of thermal and/or oxidative decomposition. When the temperature becomes so high as to break the protective "jacket", the polyethylene backbone would rapidly decompose, as evidenced by the sharp slope of the TGA curve in the

high temperature range. No glass transition temperature was detected by DSC analysis. This might be again because of the rigid "jacket" which forces the polymer main chain to take a stiffened conformation, preventing the segmental movements from happening.

Fig. 2. ^1H NMR spectra of (A) (methyl-1-naphthyl-phenylsilyl)ethylene monomer and (B) its polymer (CDCl_3 , rt; sample from Table 1 no. 2).

Fig. 3. TGA thermogram of poly[(methyl-1-naphthyl-phenylsilyl)ethylene] (in air, heating rate: $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$; sample from Table 1 no. 2).

CONCLUSION

In this study, we have synthesized a silylethylene of high optical purity via Pt-catalyzed hydrosilylation of acetylene by a chiral silane R -(+)-MeNpPhSi*H. By identifying absolute configuration of the silylethylene to be S -(+)-MeNpPhSi*Vi, we have revealed that the hydrosilylation proceeds with the retention of the configuration of the stereogenic silicon center. We have synthesized optically active poly(silylethylene)s by polymerizing either the chiral monomer using an achiral initiator (n -BuLi) or the racemic monomer using a chiral initiator [n -BuLi/(-)-sparteine]. All the polymers possess very narrow molecular weight distributions (M_w/M_n down to 1.02). The sign (+ or -)

and magnitude of the optical rotation of the polymers can be "tuned" by changing the catalyst system and the polymerization temperature. The polymers are thermally stable, possess high glass transition temperature, and may find a wide range of hi-tech applications as specialty materials. For example, the optically active polymers may be used as chiral dopants in non-linear optical systems and chiral commanding layers in liquid crystalline display devices.

Acknowledgments—This project was in part supported by a research grant from the Hong Kong Government Research Grants Council (HKUST597/95P). We would also like to thank the Center for Display Research of our University (HKUST) and the Hong Kong Industry Department for their financial support.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Abe and K. Inomata. In *Polymer Handbook* (edited by J. Brandrup and E. H. Immergut), 3rd ed. p. VII/561. Wiley, New York (1989).
- [2] F. Ciardelli. In *Encyclopedia of Polymer Science and Engineering* (edited by J. I. Kroschwitz), 2nd ed. Vol. 10, p. 463. Wiley, New York (1985).
- [3] R. Schulz and E. Kaiser. *Adv. Polym. Sci.* **4**, 236 (1965).
- [4] M. C. Petty, M. R. Bryce and D. Bloor. *Introduction to Molecular Electronics*. Edward Arnold, London (1995).
- [5] B. Z. Tang and N. Kotera. *Macromolecules* **22**, 4388 (1989).
- [6] B. Z. Tang and N. Kotera. Japanese Patent H2-258807 (1990).
- [7] *Advanced Materials* **2**, 107 (1990).
- [8] V. Gevorgyan, L. Borisova, J. Popelis, E. Lukevics, Z. Foltynowicz, J. Gulinski and B. Marciniak. *J. Organomet. Chem.* **424**, 15 (1992).
- [9] I. Ojima. In *The Chemistry of Organic Silicon Compounds* (edited by S. Patai and Z. Rappoport), Part 2, Chap. 25. Wiley, New York (1989).
- [10] L. H. Sommer, C. L. Frye, G. A. Parker and K. W. Michael. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **86**, 3271 (1964).
- [11] A. Holt, A. W. P. Jarvie and G. J. Jervis. *J. Organomet. Chem.* **21**, 75 (1970).
- [12] R. Corriu and G. Royo. *Tetrahedron* **27**, 4289 (1971).
- [13] Y. Okamoto and T. Nakano. *Chem. Rev.* **94**, 349 (1994).
- [14] Q. F. Zhou, X. Wan, D. Zhang and X. D. Feng. In *Liquid Crystalline Polymer Systems* (edited by A. I. Isayev, T. Kyu and S. Z. D. Cheng), Series 632, Chap. 20, p. 345. Am. Chem. Soc. Washington, D. C. (1976).